

Organizational Agility Assessment to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Structure Streamlining and Implementation of “Team of Teams” as the New Way of Working in the West Java Provincial Government

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to conduct an organizational agility assessment in the Regional Secretariat of the West Java Provincial Government through Five Trademarks of Agile Organization, i.e. Strategy, Structure, Process, People, and Technology. Five Trademarks comprises 23 agile practices and is represented by 40 questionnaire statements. This research involves respondents from the civil servants serving in the Regional Secretariat of West Java. The respondent determination used complex probability sampling and stratified into 9 units of groups, with a sample of 211 employees. Using descriptive statistical analysis, this study shows that the Regional Secretariat is categorized as an average level in terms of organizational agility, with high stable capability and average dynamic capability. The Process and People dimension should be the main concern to enhance the current organizational agility level.

KEYWORDS: Agile organization, agility assessment, Five Trademarks of Agile Organization, Regional Secretariat of West Java Provincial Government, Structure streamlining.

INTRODUCTION

Bureaucracy reform in Indonesia is one of the five priority programs promised by the President of Indonesia, Joko Widodo, revealed in his first political speech after being reelected in 2019. The President demanded to make organizational reform through structure streamlining, making all the government institutions leaner at any level, agile, upholding a new mindset, a new way of working, and speed of services. Thus, structure streamlining in all government institutions becomes an important agenda that must be obeyed by all provincial, regency, and city governments in Indonesia.

The Central Government of Indonesia (2014) divides managerial positions for civil servants’ careers into two types i.e. administrative, and high leadership positions. The administrative type is divided into the administrator (manager) and supervisory positions called Echelon III and Echelon IV. While the high leadership position is known as Echelon I and Echelon II. The West Java Provincial Government specifically in the Regional Secretariat decided organizational streamlining conducted in two phases. The first phase was held in December 2021, followed by the second phase in June 2022. In total, 103 out of 108 administrative positions at Echelon III and Echelon IV in the Regional Secretariat shifted to functional positions, leaving only 5 managerial positions at Echelon III.

Table 1. Recap of Streamlining Structure in West Java Regional Secretariat

Position	Prior Structure	Streamlining Structure		Total Streamlined	Maintained
		Phase I	Phase II		
Echelon IV	81	51	30	81	0
Echelon III	27	0	22	22	5
Echelon II	15	0	0	0	15
Echelon I	1	0	0	0	1
Total	124	51	52	103	21

After a massive structure streamlining, the West Java Provincial Government (2021) implemented a new way of working model called “Team of Teams” adopted from the concept pointed out by General Stanley McChrystal (2015) to encourage the emergence of agile practices. Relatively few government organizations are likely to have the capability and know-how to implement all the elements of a comprehensive agile transformation (Dib et al., 2022). However, the core agile principles can be applied and integrated in particular ways across different levels of government to enhance both performance and productivity to create a better public service experience for the citizens (Dib et al., 2022).

According to Wendler (2014), to manage the transition to an agile organization which is considered a complex and strategic task, the management has to execute the following three steps continuously:

1. Assess the current level of organizational agility;
2. Identifying potential areas for improvement; and
3. Planning, executing, and monitoring appropriate improvement actions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This research started by finding general issues in the West Java Provincial Government through regulatory and internal document review, FGD, and interviews with relevant stakeholders. A literature review was conducted to examine three proposed models by evaluating their respective strengths and weaknesses i.e. Organizational Health Index (OHI), Organizational Agility Maturity Model (OAMM), and the Five Trademarks of Agile Organization. McKinsey’s Five Trademarks of Agile Organization is applied to this research to assess organizational agility (OA) since it offers a valuable conceptual framework to assess the core principles and key characteristics of agile organizations. Collected data through the survey conducted in the West Java Regional Secretariat being analyzed to formulate several proposals for agility improvement.

Figure 1. Research Design

B. Conceptual Framework

The designed questionnaire refers to McKinsey’s five trademarks of an agile organization, which comprise the elements of strategy, structure, process, people, and technology. Each trademark of an agile organization has intrinsic value that is translated into an emerging set of 23 agile practices.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework of Organizational Agility

C. Methodology

The methodology used in this study is quantitative research by analyzing collected data through offline and online surveys from 24th October to 20th November 2023. The respondent determination used complex probability with stratified random sampling, whereby the total population was divided into meaningful subgroups, and then drawn proportionally according to the original size of the population (Sekaran et al., 2016). The advantage of stratification is the researcher able to make comparisons among groups (Sekaran et al., 2016). Total population stratified by function into 9 existing Bureau following the West Java Governor Regulation (2022) i.e. Biro Pemerintahan dan Otonomi Daerah (OTDA), Biro Kesejahteraan Rakyat (KESRA), Biro Hukum dan Hak Asasi Manusia (HUKHAM), Biro Perekonomian (EKO), Biro Badan Usaha Milik Daerah, Investasi dan Administrasi Pembangunan (BIA), Biro Pengadaan Barang dan Jasa (PBJ), Biro Organisasi (ORG), Biro Administrasi Pimpinan (ADPIM), and Biro Umum (UMUM). There are 691 total employees, however, the respondents who filled out the survey were only 211 sample size accounted for a 5.75% error rate by using the Slovin’s formula.

The questionnaire designed covers both stable and dynamic capabilities which consists of 23 agile practices represented by 40 statements that ask respondents extent whether they agree or disagree using a 5-point Likert scale (Neuman, 2014). The result of each item is calculated from the mean value and classified into five categories with a 0.8 interval scale range.

Table 2. OA Interval Scale Range

Score	Category
$1.00 < X \leq 1.80$	Very Low
$1.81 < X \leq 2.60$	Low
$2.61 < X \leq 3.40$	Average
$3.41 < X \leq 4.20$	High
$4.21 < X \leq 5.00$	Very High

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Validity and Reliability Testing

The correlation technique used to test the validity of the statement items in this study is Pearson Product Moment. The result shows that all statement items have a validity coefficient greater than r_{table} 0,138. Hence, it can be concluded that all statement items are proven valid which can be used in further analysis. Reliability testing is carried out by testing the instrument once, which is then analyzed using the Alpha-Cronbach method. The questionnaire is considered reliable if the coefficient is greater than 0.7 (Sekaran et al., 2016). The output of SPSS shows the reliability of a coefficient is 0,958. This indicates the models/tools to use in excellent reliability.

B. Survey Result Analysis on Organizational Agility

On the OA assessment, the total score obtained is 28597 and the mean value of the responses regarding the OA variable is 3.38. The score interpretation criteria on the OA variable can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 3. OA Assessment Variable Continuum Line

Organizational agility in the Regional Secretariat is categorized at an average level. The table below shows the mean score of the organizational agility in each dimension or trademark.

Table 3. OA Score in Each Dimension

Dimension	Mean	Category
Strategy	3.46	High
Structure	3.49	High
Process	3.34	Average
People	3.25	Average
Technology	3.34	Average

Two out of the five dimensions measured, i.e. strategy and structure, are categorized as “high” with scores of 3.46 and 3.49 respectively. Meanwhile, the other three dimensions i.e. process, people, and technology are categorized as “average” with scores of 3.34, 3.25, and 3.34 respectively. Based on the measurement results on each dimension, the structure gets the highest score with 3.49 and the people dimension gets the lowest score with 3.25.

Regarding the descriptive statistics analysis on each dimension, the mean value of the answers given by the respondents is analyzed to gain a deeper understanding of the assessment results of each agile practice. Descriptive discussion includes the dimensions of strategy, structure, process, people, and technology which covers 23 agile practices.

Strategy: The strategy dimension covers 4 agile practices consisting of 9 item statements. The total score is 6520 and the mean value of the responses regarding the strategy dimension is 3.46. The score interpretation criteria on the strategy dimension can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 4. Strategy Dimension Continuum Line

Respondents’ answer regarding the strategy dimension in the Regional Secretariat is categorized at a high level. The following table is the recap of the mean value on strategy dimension regarding its indicator or each of agile practices.

Table 4. Mean Value of Agile Practices in the Strategy Dimension

Strategy Practices	Mean Value	Category
Shared Purpose and Vision	3,60	High
Sense and Seize Opportunities	3,61	High
Flexible Resource Allocation	3,24	Average
Clear, Actionable Strategic Guidance	3,38	Average

Based on Table 4. of the mean value of agile practices in the strategy dimension, the highest value is obtained by the “sense and seize opportunities” practice which is classified as dynamic capability for 3.61 and categorized as high. Meanwhile, the lowest value obtained by the ”flexible resource allocation” practice which is classified as dynamic capability for 3.24 and categorized as average.

Structure: The structure dimension covers 7 agile practices consisting of 12 item statements. The total score is 8847 and the mean value of the responses regarding the structure dimension is 3.49. The score interpretation criteria on the structure dimension can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 5. Structure Dimension Continuum Line

Respondents’ answer regarding the structure dimension in the Regional Secretariat is categorized at a high level. The following table is a recap of the mean value on structure dimension regarding its indicator or each agile practice.

Table 5. Mean Value of Agile Practices in Structure Dimension

Structure Practices	Mean Value	Category
Clear, Flat Structure	3,65	High
Clear, Accountable Roles	3,63	High
Hands-on Governance	3,45	High
Robust Communities of Knowledge and Practices	3,35	Average
Active Partnership and Ecosystem	3,61	High
Open Physical and Virtual Environment	3,35	Average
Fit-for-purpose Accountable Cells	3,41	High

Based on Table 5. of the mean value of agile practices in the structure dimension, the highest value is obtained by the “clear and flat structure” practice which is classified as stable capability for 3.65 and categorized as high. Meanwhile, the lowest value obtained by ”open physical and virtual environment” practices which is classified as dynamic capability for 3.35 and categorized as an average.

Process: The process dimension covers 6 agile practices consisting of 10 item statements. The total score is 7023 and the mean value of the responses regarding the process dimension is 3.34. The score interpretation criteria on the process dimension can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 6. Process Dimension Continuum Line

Respondents’ answer regarding process dimension in the Regional Secretariat is categorized at an average level. The following table is a recap of the mean value on process dimension regarding its indicator or each agile practice.

Table 6. Mean Value of Agile Practices in the Process Dimension

Process Practices	Mean Value	Category
Standardized Ways of Working	3,27	Average
Performance Orientation	3,47	High
Rapid Iteration and Experimentation	3,40	Average
Information Transparency	3,14	Average
Continuous Learning	3,21	Average
Quick, Efficient, and Continuous Decision-making	3,52	High

Based on Table 6. of the mean value of agile practices in the process dimension, the highest value is obtained by the “quick, efficient, and continuous decision-making” practice which is classified as dynamic capability for 3.52 and categorized as high. Meanwhile, the lowest value obtained by the ”information transparency” practice which is classified as dynamic capability for 3.14 and categorized as an average.

People: The people dimension covers 4 agile practices consisting of 6 item statements. The total score is 4100 and the mean value of the responses regarding the people dimension is 3.25. The score interpretation criteria on the people dimension can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 7. People Dimension Continuum Line

Respondents’ answers regarding the people dimension in the Regional Secretariat are categorized at an average level. The following table is a recap of the mean value on the people dimension regarding its indicator or each agile practice.

Table 7. Mean Value of Agile Practices in the People Dimension

People Practices	Mean Value	Category
Shared and Servant Leadership	3,21	Average
Cohesive Community	3,39	Average
Entrepreneurial Leadership	3,53	High
Role Mobility	2,88	Average

Based on Table 7. of the mean value of agile practices in the people dimension, the highest value is obtained by the “entrepreneurial leadership” practice which is classified as stable capability for 3.53 and categorized as high. Meanwhile, the lowest value obtained by ”role mobility” practices which is classified as dynamic capability for 2.88 and categorized as an average.

Technology: The technology dimension covers 2 agile practices consisting of 3 item statements. The total score is 2107 and the mean value of the responses regarding the technology dimension is 3.34. The score interpretation criteria on the technology dimension can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 8. Technology Dimension Continuum Line

Respondents’ answer regarding the technology dimension in the Regional Secretariat is categorized at an average level. The following table is a recap of the mean value on the technology dimension regarding its indicator or each agile practice.

Table 8. Mean Value of Agile Practices in the Technology Dimension

Technology Practices	Mean Value	Category
Evolving Technology Architecture, Systems, and Tools	3,37	Average
Next-generation Technology Development and Delivery Practices	3,31	Average

Based on Table 8. the mean value of two practices in the technology dimension, namely “evolving technology architecture, systems, and tools” and “next-generation technology development and delivery” practices are classified as dynamic capability and categorized as an average with a mean value of 3.37 and 3.31 respectively.

OA on Each Bureau: Regarding the descriptive statistics analysis on each bureau or unit, the mean value of the answers given by the respondents is analyzed to gain a deeper understanding of the assessment results. The descriptive discussion illustrates the stable and dynamic capability of each bureau to map its position in the quadrant whether it falls into the trapped, start-up, bureaucratic, or agile category. The following table shows the mean value of each bureau regarding its stable and dynamic capability.

Table 9. Mean Value Based on Each Bureau/Unit

Unit	Stability		Dynamic	
	Mean	Category	Mean	Category
ADPIM	3,74	High	3,63	High
BIA	3,82	High	3,68	High
HUKHAM	3,46	High	3,33	Average
KESRA	3,64	High	3,49	High
ORG	3,39	Average	3,15	Average

Unit	Stability		Dynamic	
	Mean	Category	Mean	Category
PEMOTDA	3,58	High	3,47	High
PBJ	2,81	Average	2,65	Average
EKO	3,33	Average	3,16	Average
UMUM	3,61	High	3,43	High

The highest score of stable capability is obtained by BIA at 3.82 while the lowest score is obtained by PBJ at 2.81. Meanwhile, in the dynamic capability, the highest score was also obtained by BIA at 3.68 and the lowest score obtained by PBJ at 2.65. Each unit also consistently exhibits a greater stable capability than its dynamic capability. The interpretation of each bureau's score in terms of stable and dynamic capability in the scattergram can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 9. OA Mapping by Bureau/Unit

OA assessment results of the 9 units or bureaus show different results. Five units are classified as "agile", namely ADPIM, BIA, KESRA, PEMOTDA, and UMUM. One unit is classified as "bureaucratic" namely HUKHAM. Additionally, there are 3 units with stable and dynamic capability at an average level considered as "trapped".

Table 10. OA Category of Each Unit

Unit	Legend	Category
ADPIM	A	Agile
BIA	B	Agile
HUKHAM	C	Bureaucratic
KESRA	D	Agile
ORG	E	Trapped
PEMOTDA	F	Agile
PBJ	G	Trapped
EKO	H	Trapped
UMUM	I	Agile

C. Discussion

The people and process dimension should be the main concern of the West Java Regional Secretariat in improving its organizational agility. Within the people dimension *role mobility*, and *shared and servant leadership* had the lowest score among other agile practices. Whereas in the process dimension *information transparency* and *continuous learning* are practices that require strong emphasis.

Role mobility allows employees to have flexibility and control over their career paths (Williamson et al., 2023). It enables people to rotate regularly both vertically and horizontally across different roles and teams based on their interests and personal development goals (Aghina et al., 2015). The leadership style in an agile organization prioritizes collaboration, empathy, empowering, and developing others (Aghina et al., 2015). Servant leaders share their power and commitment, put the needs of others ahead, and help people to reach their utmost potential and perform as highly as possible by encouraging, supporting, and empowering them (Yang et al., 2017). This type of leader also can act as a catalyst that encourages people to take action in a team-oriented ways and be involved in strategic decision-making (Aghina et al., 2015). Internal Talent Marketplaces (ITMs) and Servant Leadership Training, Coaching, and Mentoring are proposed to improve these two agile practices in the people dimension.

Hereafter, agile organizations require full transparency of information, ensuring that every team can have quick and easy access to the information they need (Aghina et al., 2015). According to Wendler (2014), effective knowledge management is needed to rapidly and accurately adapt to any unexpected change. Therefore, a knowledge management system complemented by a culture of trust and psychological safety is needed to increase information transparency. In addition, continuous learning also ensures everyone can freely learn from their own and other failures and successes. Hence, a regular opportunity to exchange information and work experiences, and allow employees to allocate dedicated time to innovate is needed to improve these two agile practices in the process dimension.

Sequentially, the business solutions proposed to improve role mobility, shared and servant leadership, information transparency, and continuous learning are outlined below.

1. Internal Talent Marketplaces (ITMs)

ITMs needed to facilitate seamless role mobility, match employees with roles, and allow executives to access diverse perspectives on key projects or assignments (Cogwill et al., 2023). In addition, ITMs enhance skills development and increase job satisfaction and engagement by providing a centralized platform for talent management (Cogwill et al., 2023). ITMs should provide information to match employees with available roles, tasks, or projects based on their interests, capabilities, and personal development goals. West Java Provincial Government currently has an existing talent management system to manage the career of civil servants, hence the ITMs feature can be incorporated into it to connect key projects with talents. However, to facilitate seamless role mobility, it is important to make several adjustments to the current performance management system, career management system, and reward system.

2. Servant Leadership Training, Coaching, and Mentoring

The West Java Provincial Government is currently initiating a program called Jabar Leadership Program (JLP) to create future leaders and Jabar Development Program (JDP) to improve the knowledge and capability of existing leaders. Shared and servant leadership lessons need to be incorporated into this program to shape and develop current and future leaders' competencies. Hereafter, the West Java Provincial Government is also required to hire professional coaches who are certified and have professional experience to conduct coaching sessions for existing leaders to foster the character and mindset of shared and servant leaders. Professional coaches from outsiders will provide new insights and perspectives for the organization. In addition, mentoring from senior leaders is needed to provide an example to others by exemplifying the behavior of shared and servant leadership in their daily activities, demonstrating humbleness, empathy, and focus on serving others, creating a role model for others to be followed.

3. Knowledge Management

An agile organization should be able to manage all the resources of information and knowledge to encourage a fast decision-making process based on valid data or information. Information flow has to consider both physical and non-physical aspects. Physical aspects relate to IT infrastructure that allows everyone to communicate and collaborate effectively, and data banks that can be accessed whenever it is needed. West Java Provincial Government has already used an existing data bank called "Satu Data Jabar", however, this IT infrastructure needs to be complemented by non-physical aspects related to organizational culture, where individuals are open to sharing information and knowledge. In addition, a psychologically safe climate is essential to ensure that

employees can freely contribute ideas, share relevant information, and report any issues that occur within the organization (Edmondson, 2019).

4. Townhall Meeting and Innovation Program

To improve continuous learning practices, the Regional Secretariat of West Java needs to provide a forum or town hall meeting periodically for employees to share experiences, where each individual can freely learn from each other's successes and failures. Trust and psychological safety are also needed as non-physical or cultural aspects to ensure this practice runs well. In addition to fostering a learning mindset, the Regional Secretariat of West Java should allow employees to spend dedicated time for instance one day a week to work on something out of their routine, to innovate, and improve the business process. Rewards need to be given to employees who are considered successful through the existing reward mechanism.

CONCLUSION

Following the results of the analysis and discussion carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. Organizational agility in the Regional Secretariat of West Java in aggregate has a total score of 28597, and the mean value of respondents' answers regarding the OA assessment variable is 3.38, which is categorized as average. Regional Secretariat of West Java classified as bureaucratic according to current high stable capability and average dynamic capability.
2. The highest mean value is obtained at the Structure dimension at 3.49 which is classified as high. The lowest mean value is obtained at the People dimension at 3.25 which is classified as an average, followed by Process dimension at 3.34. Role mobility, shared and servant leadership, information transparency, and continuous learning are the main concerns of agile practices to improve organizational agility in the West Java Regional Secretariat.
3. West Java Regional Secretariat needs Internal Talent Marketplaces (ITMs) to improve role mobility and facilitate it seamlessly. Meanwhile, training, coaching, and mentoring programs are needed to improve shared and servant leadership practices incorporated in JDP and JLP programs. In addition, both physical and non-physical knowledge management needed to improve information transparency, complemented by town hall meetings and innovation programs to ensure a continuous learning mindset arises.

In navigating the transition to an agile organization, the West Java Regional Secretariat should apply the change management process to ensure the new structural and cultural change is well-embraced by all employees. The top management should recognize the needs of every individual to engage, embrace, and adopt the new organizational design (Hiatt et al., 2012). Devoid the presence of change management, and lack of attempt to drive every individual's involvement, even perfectly designed structures, processes, technologies, and job roles will generate no performance advancement and added value to the organization (Hiatt et al., 2012). Hence it would be essential to make each adopt new values, skills, and accompanied by behavioral change. (Hiatt et al., 2012)

In addition, the recommendation for further research is on the relationship between stable capability and dynamic capability. These research findings show there is a positive relationship between stable and dynamic capabilities. From the scatterplot outlined in Figure 9, units with higher stable capabilities have demonstrated greater dynamic capabilities as well. This finding reinforces the argument that organizational agility is not only dependent on dynamic capabilities, instead agility, especially in large organizations, needs to exhibit both stable and dynamic capabilities at the same time (Aghina et al., 2015).

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